

Building Adaptive Capacity in this series of Beyond-Surge-Capacity Outbreaks: Reconfiguration under pressure at multiple levels simultaneously

1. Clinicians are the source of resilient performance in the face of surges.

Scale of the demand requires other parts of health care related organizations to join clinicians and become sources of resilient performance. These groups are not practiced at high tempo operations.

2. The disease is novel leading to active pursuit of information to learn and and adjust care practices.

The novelty of disease is basic and requires careful adjustment of various parts of clinical repertoire of knowledge/techniques despite limited information and uncertainty about the disease. New aspects of disease progression and risk become apparent as patients present and are cared for. Every one understands that learning is ongoing and they are open to modify their protocols as new information arrives and as they gain experience.

One physician commenting on the need for agility: "it will be very interesting to see how well we adapt and how well we can basically digest information, analyze it, and get it to the bedside."

3. Reconfiguration of care for non-Covid-19 patients within their scope of responsibility.

The medical centers are busy without Covid-19. Accommodating their non-Covid-19 patients and protecting them from the virus remains within their scope of care. Some aspects of care for these populations can be deferred or shifted to tele-health format, though the reconfiguration brings workload costs and risks. Their patients can have conditions which increase risk from Covid-19 infection which requires separation of the two populations' care streams.

The load on the health care delivery system in any area increases since delivery needs to be reconfigured into two separate care streams for the two populations – non-Covid-19 patients and Covid-19 patients. This means resources also are needed to monitor for and prevent any sneak paths which would expose other ill patients from exposure to the virus. Examples of sneak paths leading to contamination of areas of the hospital from undiagnosed Covid-19 patients have been reported.

4. Active pursuit of information to learn and adapt - horizontal lines of communication

The emergence of or repurposing of horizontal communication among physician groups is ongoing including informal networks to share information. Need early recognition of new developments but also need cross checks and corroboration of new emerging information. This is commonplace in adapting to new challenges.

Knowing about Covid-19 disease and treatment from groups already experiencing the outbreak is not the same as the *know how* that comes from actually treating Covid patients in ICU (knowing how skills vs knowing about).

5. Anticipating bottlenecks ahead leads to actions that create a readiness to respond

As clinicians work through and modify care protocols, they are choosing methods that also create the ability to act when/should bottlenecks arise. And this is evident at multiple levels / scales in parallel as actions are taken to build up the capability to handle Covid-19 patient surges.

6. Reconfiguration of Coordination Across Roles

They have had to extensively reconfigure how they work across roles to maximize the effectiveness of expertise, personnel, critical equipment, etc. This means lot's of adjustments across levels who have to interact and coordinate much more tightly. Lots of standard ways of doing things are too rigid or too slow. And they know they will have to adapt what they have already modified as they face whatever surge they will experience. They are adopting new kinds of coordination tools (eg electronic tools like Slack), and these change how they experience and manage the costs of coordination. The need to update the various players creates the problem of lag and confusion as updates occur. Potential for coordination breakdowns already evident – how to minimize these and how to recover quickly is important.

One example is how new roles are created to get assistance: immunocompromised experts moved to tele-health; newly graduated medical students are allowed to take on some medical responsibilities early. These adaptations add capability but also impose coordination and training burdens.

7. Updating

Keeping pace with the changes in official information is a challenge and a burden (in U.S.: CDC -> state Departments of Health -> hospital -> clinicians). Notifications to already busy personnel have to be consumed, lead to changes, interact or conflict with other information, may be stale, and can result in need to modify practices of care teams. Getting lost in the stream is a risk and adaptations will arise to compensate.

8. Working beyond nominal deployable surge capacity

The maximum capacity -- or just getting toward what they think might be their max capacity -- is well beyond anything they have ever done before and beyond what they think is good way to do things, except they have to find a way to treat those who need care. This is the fundamental responsibility of the clinicians - find a way to treat the people who are there and need care. As a result they exhibit high initiative to keep up delivery of care as load increases. A variety of breakdowns can occur when they have to move to a new ways of working, with new forms of interaction, under new levels of stress.

9. Offsetting Personnel Attrition

Clinician capabilities are under stress beyond the normal pressure on health care systems already working near capacity. Sustaining performance during a surge is difficult and the

inability to provide support (work/rest cycles) increases dropout from exhaustion (also produces other negative effects on ability to coordinate activity, missing updates, reduced ability to adapt to new information). Dropout occurs as clinicians get the disease. Clinicians still need to cover their care responsibilities to non-Covid population. More extensive coordination, interaction, information exchanges have to go on across roles, levels, and organizations using new means for interaction that impose their own workload costs. These three forms of stress – (a) reconfigure and provide care for non-Covid-19 patients, (b) expand and deliver care for Covid-19 patients, and (c) reconfigure how they work together to meet the scale of demands – occur together adding to the overload potential and can undermine the capability to provide care effectively.

The ability to sustain performance under these stressors can be supported but requires the development of means to rotate and support clinical workers in advance. The methods to sustain performance are hobbled when there is insufficient PPE (protective gear).

10. New Ways to be Responsive at Scale while Injecting Sufficient Thoroughness

All of the above highlight the need to be highly responsive to emerging needs, information, conditions, and threats. However, there is still the need to cross check, corroborate, follow up to assess that the actions being considered do not have offsetting negative side effects. This is changing the speed-thoroughness trade-off relative to other trade-off dimensions.